

Effect of Temperature on the Adsorption of Some Dyes on Kaolinite

D. K. De, S. K. Chakravarti* and S. K. Mukherjee**

The adsorption of cationic dyes viz., crystal violet, malachite green and methylene blue was measured on kaolinite ($<2.0\mu$ average size fraction) at three different temperatures. The amount of crystal violet and malachite green adsorbed increased with temperature but that of methylene blue remained constant within the limits of experimental error. The heats of adsorption calculated from the isotherms varied between -2.6 and -8.7 K. Cals/mole. The heats of adsorption attain a maximum at a particular concentration for each dye and then gradually becomes smaller with increasing amount of the dye adsorbed.

Adsorption processes are in general exothermic.¹⁻³ Different techniques were used by different workers to measure the differential heat of adsorption. Constant environment micro-calorimeter² has been used to measure the heat of adsorption of organic vapours on reduced and oxidized iron. Kiselev *et al* used constant heat exchange calorimeter³ for the adsorption of sphere-like molecules, viz., CH_4 , CCl_4 on carbon black. Besides this, vacuum liquid microburette³ was employed to measure CCl_4 adsorption and the gas volume method for neopentane adsorption.

In the case of solution phase adsorption Bartell, Tudor, Thomas and Yang Fu⁴ observed that the solubility of the adsorbates is one of the main factors which control the adsorption. They showed in the case of adsorption of some aliphatic substances of low molecular weight on carbon that at low concentration of the adsorbate the exothermicity of the process is prominent, so that adsorption decreases with increase of temperature. But at high concentration of the adsorbate, adsorption increases with the increase of temperature, if the solubility of the adsorbate decreases with rise of temperature.

The adsorption of crystal violet on hydrated ferric oxide sol⁵ is seen to increase with the temperature though the effect was not very marked at the low

*Present Address—Department of Chemistry, North Bengal Univ., P. O. Raja Rammohanpur, Dist. Darjeeling.

**Present Address—Department of Agriculture, Calcutta Univ., 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Calcutta-19.

1. V. Kevorkian and R. O. Steiner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 3.
2. Yung Fang and Yu Yao, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 10.
3. N. N. Avgul, G. I. Berezin, A. V. Kiselev and I. A. Lygina, *Zhur. Fiz. Khim.*, 1956, 30, 2116 (C. A. 51 6309 f)
4. F. E. Bartell, L. Tudor, Thomas and Ying Fu, *J. Phys. and Colloid Chem.*, 1951, 1456.
5. R. B. Hajela and S. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 1.

concentration of the adsorbate. The adsorption of tetradecylamine on calcite, limonite and magnetite⁶ shows, however, a different result. With the rise of temperature the adsorption of the amine on limonite decreases, on calcite it increases at 10-25°, while at still higher temperatures it decreases. With magnetite there is practically no change in adsorption.

In the present communication the results of adsorption of some cationic dyes such as crystal violet (C. V.), malachite green (M. G.) and methylene blue (M. B.) on kaolinite at three different temperatures are reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

The kaolinite fraction ($<2.0\mu$) was isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation of Rajmahal kaolinite (supplied by the Calcutta Minerals Supply Co. Ltd.). This clay was converted into the H-form by H-resin (IR-120) treatment.

The exchange capacity was measured by the $BaCl_2-Ba(OH)_2$ method on the basis of 110° oven dry material. Crystal violet was of E. Merck quality, malachite green was obtained from BDH and methylene blue from U.S.S.R. They were used as such without further purification. Stoppered bottles were taken with 10 ml. clay suspension in each (4.4% for M.G. and 3.06% for M.B. and C.V. adsorptions). Different amounts of the dye solutions were added to the suspension, shaken for two hours in a mechanical shaker kept in a thermostat and allowed to equilibrate overnight. They were again shaken next day for two hours at the same temperature, and the suspensions were centrifuged at the room temperature, (2000 r.p.m.) for five minutes. In order that the suspensions were not exposed for a long time to the room temperature, the supernatant liquids were rapidly transferred after 5 minutes to different centrifuge tubes. The main portion of the exchange material was then separated from the supernatant liquid which was again centrifuged for fifteen minutes to make the solution free from the remaining particles of clay. The clear supernatant liquid was analysed colorimetrically for the dye content using the Spekker (Hilger). The dye adsorbed was calculated by difference. The experiments with clay—C.V. system were done at temperatures 30°, 40° and 51°, clay—M.G. system at 29°, 40° and 49°. For the clay—M.B. system the temperatures were 30° and 50°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adsorption isotherms of M.G., C.V., and M.B. at different temperatures are shown in figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively. It can be seen from figs. 1 and 2 that the adsorption of M.G. and C.V. increases with the rise of temperature. But with M.B.

6. S. I. Mitrofanov and V. G. Kushnikova, *Sb. Tr. Gos. Nanchn-Issled-Inst. Tsvetn Metal*, 1962, No. 19, 15. (C. A. 60, 3520 b)

(fig.3) no change of adsorption seems to take place, within the limits of experimental error, with temperature. All the isotherms more or less fit in with the Langmuir

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of M. G. on kaolinite at different temperatures.

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherms of C. V. on kaolinite at different temperatures.

adsorption equation, except the measurements at the lowest and the highest concentrations of the dyes. The heat of adsorption has been calculated from the equation

$$Q = \frac{RT_1 T_2}{T_1 - T_2} \ln \frac{C_1}{C_2}$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the concentrations of the dye absorbed at temperatures T_1 and T_2 , corresponding to the same initial concentration. The values of C_1 and C_2 are found out from the figs. 1 and 2. It can be seen that the heats of adsorption

lie between -2.0 and -9.0 K Cals/mole. Fig 4 shows that the heats of adsorption pass through a maximum when plotted against amounts adsorbed. The maximum

Fig. 3. Adsorption isotherm of M. B. on kaolinite.

Fig. 4. Variation of the heats of adsorption with the amounts of dye adsorbed. The graph and the ordinate on the right hand side are for the adsorption of M. G. on kaolinite. The graph and ordinate on the left hand side are for the adsorption of C. V. on kaolinite.

heat of adsorption corresponds to the binding of the adsorbate ions to the higher energy binding sites of the adsorbent. This binding is apparently facilitated when the concentration of the adsorbate reaches a certain value corresponding to the maximum of the curves. Beyond this point further adsorption takes place on the low energy sites and hence the corresponding heat of adsorption is also small.

In adsorption process the dissociation of the associated molecules is important. Dye molecules are in the associated form at a higher concentration⁷. As the adsorption of the dissociated dye molecules take place, more and more of the aggregates dissociate, so that stage by stage the heats of dissociation of the aggregated dye molecules are included in the calculated heat of adsorption. Majury⁸ examined quantitatively the successive heat changes in solution adsorption of some dyes on cellulose acetates. The calculated heats are naturally the apparent heat of adsorption but not the actual ones. The adsorption of two dyes, viz., janus red and lissamine green from water on to inorganic surfaces is found to be apparently endothermic⁹ as the saturation adsorption rises with temperature. But from a dissociating solvent like methanol the amount adsorbed falls with rise of temperature. According to the authors⁹ the apparent endothermic nature of the adsorption is a result of the aggregation of the dye molecules in solution. In the case of M. B. adsorption on kaolinite it may be such that the adsorption process is itself exothermic but the dissociation of the dye molecules is an endothermic process, so that the two balance each other resulting in no change of heat of adsorption. It has been observed by Giles, Easton and Mckay¹⁰ that adsorption of ethyl violet on alumina increases with temperature, that of sufranine-T decreases with temperature but no change was observed with M.B.

The adsorption of dyes is therefore controlled mainly by such factors as association, solubility and adsorption proper of the dye molecules.

All the measurements were reproducible within 5% except at the lowest levels of concentration. In that case also the error did not exceed 10%. All the glass vessels used were of pyrex brand so that the error due to adsorption on the glass surfaces was small. The temperature was accurate within $\pm 1^\circ$ and maintained constant within this range.

Thanks to the authorities of the University of Kalyani for awarding a scholarship to one of us. (D. K. D.).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF KALYANI,
KALYANI, NADIA,
WEST BENGAL.

Received, May 28, 1966.

7. K. Bergmann and C. T. O'Konski, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2169.
8. T. G. Majury, *J. Soc. of Dyers and Colourists*, 1954, **70**, 442.
9. C. H. Giles, J. J. Greczek and S. N. Nakhwa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 93.
10. C. H. Giles, I. A. Easton and R. B. Mckay, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965.